

STUDENTS' COGNITIVE ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE USING DIGITAL MIND MAPPING STRATEGY

Khen Khen D. Padios ¹, Maris Jade Q. Orongan PhD ²

¹ Science Department, Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag Bukidnon

² University Town, Musuan, Maramag Bukidnon, 8710 Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15547915>

ABSTRACT

Digital Mind Mapping Strategy uses electronic graphic organizers developed and shown on computers to present, organize, generate, and classify thoughts, words, concepts, and tasks. In this context, the study examined the cognitive achievement of grade 10 students using the digital mind mapping strategy of Don Carlos National High School in the School Year 2023-2024, where thirty-seven (37) students participated in the DMMS, and twenty-nine (29) students participated in the NDMMS. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, involving a pretest and posttest design. A validated chemistry teacher-made test was used as the research instrument. To determine the students' level of cognitive achievement, descriptive statistics and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were employed to identify the significant difference between the students' cognitive achievements. The study's findings revealed that the students' cognitive achievement level was "fairly satisfactory" when exposed to the digital mind mapping strategy. Further, the analysis of covariance indicated a significant difference in cognitive achievement with an F value of 13.097 ($p < 0.05$) between the two groups. With these findings, teachers may utilize a digital mind mapping strategy to enhance students' cognitive achievement.

Keywords: *cognitive achievement, digital mind mapping*

INTRODUCTION

Science is crucial to a nation's development, contributing significantly to technological innovation and socioeconomic progress. It helps individuals become competitive, innovative, and creative. However, according to the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, the Philippines scored 365 and ranks third lowest in science literacy among the participating countries. These results showed that the country lags behind others in educational quality, particularly science education, which is consistent with the 2018 results.

Science education, particularly chemistry, faces significant challenges, including declining student interest and difficulties with abstract concepts, mathematical reasoning, and visualization (Treagust & Nieswandt, 2018). As a result, many students struggle to achieve proficiency in science, as evidenced by low performance in national assessments like the national achievement test, particularly in Don Carlos National High School (DepEd BEA, 2023), where achievement reports reveal that many junior high school students failed in science subjects due to inadequate teaching strategies or limited resources.

Don Carlos National High School (DCNHS) has consistently acknowledged the need for improvement in science education and is taking steps to bridge the learning gaps. Although past achievement reports highlight struggles, the school has initiated various programs to enhance science teaching strategies and integrate technology into instruction. Participation in science fairs, improvement of laboratory facilities, and professional development training for teachers demonstrate the school's commitment to raising the standard of science education.

In response to these challenges, innovative approaches like the digital mind mapping (DMM) strategy are being considered to address cognitive gaps. Digital mind mapping is a technology-driven teaching strategy that allows students to organize and visualize connections among ideas, making abstract scientific concepts more accessible and meaningful. According to Kumari and Mane (2022), digital mind maps foster creative thinking by enabling students to visualize relationships between concepts and enhance their ability to construct knowledge.

Despite the promising outcomes associated with the DMM strategy, exploring its effectiveness across different subjects and educational levels remains necessary. Thus, this study specifically investigates the effects of the digital mind mapping strategy on the cognitive achievement of Grade 10 Science students of Don Carlos National High School. It aims to contribute valuable insights to the field of science education by providing empirical evidence on integrating digital tools in enhancing student performance and, ultimately, supporting the broader goal of raising the quality of science education in the country.

Research Questions

This study attempted to investigate the effects of a digital mind mapping strategy (DMMS) on the cognitive achievement of Grade 10 science students at Don Carlos National High School. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the student's level of cognitive achievement, who are exposed to the digital mind mapping strategy, and those who are exposed to the non-digital mind mapping strategy in terms of;
 - a. pretest; and
 - b. posttest?
 2. Is there a significant difference in students' cognitive achievement between those who are exposed to a digital mind mapping strategy and those exposed to non-digital mind mapping with a pretest as a covariate?
-

METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes a quasi-experimental research design to investigate the effects of the DMMS on students' cognitive achievement. The researcher selected two intact heterogeneous sections of Grade 10 junior high school students. Thirty-seven (37) students participated in the DMMS group (experimental group) exposed to DMMS using Google software and learning activity sheets based on the 7E lesson plan. Twenty-nine (29) participated in the NDMMS group (control group), which used conventional teaching methods based on the 7E lesson plan. A total of sixty-six (66) students who were officially enrolled and participated in Grade 10 for the school year 2023-2024 at Don Carlos National High School, Don Carlos, Bukidnon. A pretest and posttest were administered to determine the significant difference in students' cognitive achievement when exposed to DMMS and NDMMS.

The research instrument used in this study is a researcher-made achievement test. During the fourth grading period, the researcher constructed a 70-item test covering the Gas laws and Biomolecules of Chemistry in Grade 10. The tests were content validated by three experts in chemistry: two coming from the science department of Central Mindanao University, and one public school science teacher, to determine whether the tests were appropriate in testing the students' cognitive achievement. After the content validation, the instrument underwent pilot testing for the Grade 11 students of Don Carlos National High School, who had previously completed Science 10. The test items had a reliability coefficient of 0.738, indicating good internal consistency.

Descriptive statistics such as weighted means, frequency, percentages, and standard deviation were employed to determine the students' cognitive achievement when

exposed to the digital mind mapping strategy compared to those exposed to the non-digital mind mapping strategy.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to find significant differences in students' cognitive achievement when exposed to the digital mind mapping strategy and those exposed to the non-digital mind mapping strategy. This analysis used the pretest scores as a covariate to control for any initial differences in the students' cognitive achievement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Level of Students' Cognitive Achievement exposed to Digital Mind Mapping Strategy and those exposed to Non-Digital Mind Mapping Strategy.

Raw Score	PRETEST				POSTTEST				Qualitative Interpretation
	DMMS		NDMMS		DMMS		NDMMS		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
30-35	0	0	0	0	3	8.1	0	0	Outstanding
27-29	0	0	0	0	4	10.8	0	0	Very Satisfactory
24-26	0	0	0	0	6	16.2	1	3.4	Satisfactory
21-23	2	5.4	1	3.4	7	18.9	2	6.9	Fairly Satisfactory
0-20	35	94.6	28	96.6	17	45.9	26	89.7	Did not meet the expectations
Total	37	100	37	100	29	100	29	100	
Mean	17.03		13.17		21.97		16.10		
MPS	48.64		37.63		62.78		46.01		
QI	DNME		DNME		FS		DNME		

Before the intervention, the DMMS group (N=37) had a MPS of 48.64, which falls under the qualitative interpretation of "Did not meet the expectations" (DNME). Most students in the DMMS pretest, 35 out of 37 (94.6%), scored within the 0-20 raw score range (DNME). Two students (5.4%) scored in the 21-23 range, categorized as "Fairly Satisfactory" (FS). While the NDMMS group (N=29) had a lower MPS of 37.63 at the pretest, which is interpreted as "Did not meet the expectations" (DNME). The distribution of scores shows that 28 out of 29 students (96.6%) scored in the 0-20 range (DNME), while one student (3.4%) scored in the 21-23 range (FS). Notably, a larger proportion of the NDMMS group compared to the DMMS group had no students in the higher score ranges at the pretest.

The study's findings revealed lower mean percentage scores in the pretest for the DMMS and NDMMS groups. The pretest results in Chemistry often reflect low scores due to the subject's complex and abstract nature. Furthermore, Burrows and Mooring (2015)

indicate that they frequently perceive Chemistry as difficult, which may explain the initial struggles of both groups.

The posttest results demonstrate a shift in cognitive achievement for the DMMS group. The MPS increased to 62.78, which is now categorized as "Fairly Satisfactory." The distribution of scores exhibits a positive change, with three students (8.1%) scoring in the 30-35 range (O), four students (10.8%) scoring in the 27-29 range (VS), six students (16.2%) scoring in the 24-26 range (S), and seven students (18.9%) scoring in the 21-23 range (FS). The number of students scoring in the 0-20 range (DNME) significantly decreased to 17 (45.9%). The mean scores and observed score range indicate that the digital mind mapping strategy (DMMS) may effectively enhance students' cognitive achievement. The noteworthy progress in the DMMS group's achievement, from "did not meet the expectation" to "fairly satisfactory," suggests that the mind mapping strategy has slightly improved students' cognitive achievement. However, they did not reach the "Very Satisfactory" or "Outstanding" levels. Several factors may have contributed to this, including frequent suspensions and transitions to distance learning due to high heat index conditions during the study. Additionally, student absences and disruptions from school activities may have played a role.

The NDMMS group (N=29) also demonstrated improvement in the posttest, with the MPS rising to 46.01, remaining within the "Did not meet the expectations" (DNME) category. The distribution shows that 26 students (89.7%) scored in the 0-20 range (DNME), two students (6.9%) scored in the 21-23 range (FS), and one student (3.4%) scored in the 24-26 range (S). In the NDMMS group, despite experiencing some positive effects, it did not achieve the same level of improvement, as most students still did not meet the expectations. This distribution underscores the need for more effective instructional strategies, as most students continue to fall short of expectations despite some overall score improvements. The results highlight the need for targeted help and support to enhance student achievement and ensure all learners can reach their learning objectives (Starford & Ravlikj, 2024).

The cognitive achievement outcomes between traditional and digital mind mapping strategies in science education highlight distinct differences. Although both methods improve learning, digital mind mapping frequently shows strengths in particular cognitive areas. This difference underscores the idea that in this study the digital mind mapping's unique features, such as easy sharing, observing various approaches, receiving timely feedback, and possibly incorporating multimedia, significantly enhance the learning experience and lead to greater cognitive achievement, aligning with the findings of Charles et al. (2023) and Geolien (2024).

Table 2. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Students' Cognitive Achievement

GROUP	N	MEAN	SD
Instruction using Digital Mind Mapping Strategy (DMMS)	37	62.77	13.42
Instruction Not using the Digital Mind Mapping Strategy (NDMMS)	29	46.00	10.12

TOTAL		66	55.41	14.64	
Source	SS	dF	MS	F-value	Sig.
Corrected Model	208020.634 ^a	3	69340.211	509.907	.000*
Pretest (Covariate)	801.553	1	801.553	5.894	.018
Group	3561.885	2	1780.942	13.097	.000*
Error	8567.121	63	135.986		
Total	216587.755	66			

* $p < 0.05$ ns = not significant

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on students' cognitive achievement of the posttest results for both DMMS and NDMMS groups using the pretest as the covariate. The table shows that the DMMS ($n=37$, $SD=13.42$) and NDMMS ($n=29$, $SD=10.12$) groups obtained a mean percentage score of 62.77 and 46.00, respectively.

The F-value between groups is 13.097, with a p-value of 0.000*, indicating statistical significance. The result implies that DMMS and NDMMS have different levels of cognitive achievement in Chemistry.

The findings highlight the substantial positive impact of digital mind mapping strategies on students' cognitive achievement. This study aligns with Aljaser (2017), which found statistically significant differences in posttest cognitive scores favoring the experimental group that used digital mind maps. The effect size of employing these tools was notably high. Numerous studies, including those by Umami (2016) and Mahasneh (2017), have shown that digital mind mapping enhances learning outcomes more effectively than traditional teaching methods and paper-based mind maps. In the context of English as a Foreign Language, group work using digital mind maps has proven to improve comprehension, particularly in reading tasks (Sagita et al., 2024). Additionally, digital mind mapping has been linked to positive shifts in students' attitudes toward learning (Mahasneh, 2017). These results suggest that digital mind mapping is a powerful educational tool that can significantly enhance cognitive abilities, making it a valuable strategy for educators to implement across various learning environments. By facilitating better retention of classroom material, digital mind mapping allows students to more easily recall concepts and ideas. Furthermore, it can help students save time by organizing regular writing tasks, exploring new ideas, and gaining diverse experiences, all of which contribute to their creative thinking and overall cognitive achievement.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn:

1. The student's cognitive achievement level was "fairly satisfactory" after exposure to the DMMS. Students exposed to NDMMS received a "did not meet the

expectation" result. The findings suggested that students exposed to DMMS improved their cognitive achievement after the intervention.

2. The two groups' cognitive achievement significantly differed in favor of the posttest exposed to DMMS. The grade 10 students of Don Carlos National High School exposed to DMMS had substantially higher posttest scores than those not exposed to DMMS. It shows that DMMS positively impacts the cognitive achievement of the students exposed to it.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Science teachers may explore and integrate DMMS into their lessons with different educational levels to align with curriculum objectives, and school administrators may provide teachers adequate access to digital devices and mind mapping software essential for the effective use of DMMS. They may also invest in continuous professional development programs for teachers and promote a collaborative environment to share best practices, enhancing DMMS integration and effectiveness.
2. Future researchers may explore the long-term effects of DMMS on various student demographics and educational settings, particularly its impacts on cognitive achievement and emotional and social skills, to gain a deeper understanding of its benefits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher observed ethical conduct throughout the study. Before conducting the study, the researcher secured permission from the teachers and students. Collected information remained anonymous and was stored securely. Any potential conflicts of interest between the researchers and participants were addressed and disclosed.

Acknowledgments

The researcher is deeply grateful to all who contributed to the development and success of the study. All those who helped the author conduct this study deserve deep appreciation. First, thanks are given to the Almighty for all things, particularly the blessings and wisdom granted to the researcher. To Dr. Maris Jade Q. Orongan, the mentor, is acknowledged for her invaluable guidance, patience, and unwavering support. Her insightful feedback, constructive criticism, and steadfast belief in the researcher's abilities shaped this research and guided the researcher to its completion. To Dr. Jenyliza T. Uchang, a panel member, provided valuable advice and guidance to enhance the research. To Sir Alven A. Manual, another panel member, offered helpful suggestions to refine the research. To Dr. Raul C. Orongan, the statistician, is thanked for his professional advice on data analysis. To Sir Alfons Cabrezos and Ma'am Mary Ann V. Gallo, the content and material validators, are acknowledged for their advice and

suggestions to ensure the validity of all content and materials used in the study. The principal, Ma'am Ligaya S. Gonzales, is thanked for permitting the researcher to conduct the study at the scheduled time. The Grade 10 Rizal and Mabini students of the academic year 2022-2023 are thanked for their participation in the study. The researcher sincerely appreciates the generous funding of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST-STRAND) Organization, which enabled this research. The researcher also acknowledges the unwavering support of her guiding force and faith. Through faith and belief in her abilities, she overcame challenges, persevered through setbacks, and achieved her academic goals. This thesis reflects the collective support received, for which the researcher is genuinely grateful.

REFERENCES

- Aljaser, A.M. (2017). The Effectiveness of Electronic Mind Maps in Developing Academic Achievement and the Attitude towards Learning English among Primary School Students. *International Education Studies*, 10(12), 80-95.
- Burrows, N. L., & Mooring, S. R. (2015). Using concept mapping to uncover students' knowledge structures of chemical bonding concepts. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 16(1), 53-66.
- Charles, S. B., & Aikoye, J. E. (2023). Effect of digital mind mapping on students' achievement in mathematics. 11. 1-12.
- DepEd BEA (2023). <https://assessment.deped.gov.ph/>
- Geolien, L. J. (2024). Mind Mapping on Junior High School Performance in Chemistry. *Journal of World Englishes and Educational Practices*, 6(1), 242-253
- Kumari, P., & Mane, K. (2022). Digital mind maps an innovative teaching learning strategy in science students. *Sucharitha Publication, India*, 5(2), 2277-7881
DOI: <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.05.31>
- Mahasneh, A. (2017). The effect of using electronic mind mapping on achievement and attitudes in an introduction to educational psychology course. *The new educational review*, 47(1), 295-304.
- PISA 2022 Results. (2023). <https://www.oecd.org/publication/pisa-2022-results/country-notes/philippines-a0882a2d/>
- Sagita, M., & Sagita, E. S. (2024). Enhancing English Language Learning through Digital Mind Mapping: A Comprehensive Approach for Reading Comprehension. *KIRANA: Social Science Journal*, 1(3), 142-151.
- Starford, A., & Ravlikj, I. (2024). Innovative progress tracking: Enhancing student achievement with effective interventions. *TESOL in Context*, 32(2), 5-40.
- Treagust, D. F., Duit, R., & Nieswandt, M. (2018). Sources of students' difficulties in learning Chemistry. *Educación Química* 11(2), 228-235.
- Umami, R. (2016). The Effectiveness of using Digital Mind Mapping Toward The Students' Achievement in Writing Descriptive Text to the First Grader at MAN 2 Tulungagung in Academic Year 2015/2016 (Doctoral dissertation, Thesis.

English Education Department Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training. IAIN
Tulungagung).